

MWCNT REINFORCED BIO-BASED BENZOXAZINE/EPOXY COPOLYMERS WITH NIR ACTUATION CAPABILITY

By

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Shape Memory Polymers (SMPs)

- “Remember” the original shape even after undergoing significant deformation.
- Revert back to the original shape by a suitable trigger, e.g. electromagnetic radiation, thermal energy, moisture, electricity, and pH.

Advantages of Bio-Based SMPs

Compared with conventional shape memory alloys

- ✓ Prepared from natural compounds
- ✓ Reduce consumption of petroleum-based chemicals
- ✓ High degree of deformation
- ✓ Excellent processing ability
- ✓ Great flexibility in terms of material design
- ✓ Easy control of the recovery temperature
- ✓ Adjustable shape memory transition temperature near body temperature
- ✓ Fast response

Light Stimulation on SMPs

- Light could be employed as a stimulus for SMPs, recovering their original shapes at ambient temperature.
- Polymers have to be incorporated with additive or filler such as organic dyes, ligands, gold nanoparticles, gold nanorods, and carbon nanotubes.
- Fillers absorbed light and transformed into thermal energy.

Light Stimulation Mechanism with SMPs

Molecular Mechanisms of SMP Networks

Switching Units

- ✓ Responsible for controlling the shape fixity and shape recovery
- ✓ Predetermined external stimulus

Applications of SMPs

- ❖ Medical devices such as
 - Intraocular lenses
 - Removable splints
- ❖ Shrinkable tubes
- ❖ Smart textiles
- ❖ Biomedical sensors and devices
- ❖ Deployable structures for aircraft and spacecraft

Bio-based Benzoxazine

- ❖ Solventless synthesis
- ❖ No catalyst or curing agent required
(self polymerization)
- ❖ High thermal stability
(T_d at 5wt% loss = 351–440°C)
- ❖ High char yield (32–60 %wt)
- ❖ Wide range of glass transition temperature
(T_g = 58–353°C)
- ❖ Latent curing agent for epoxy (Netpoints)
- ❖ Ability to alloy with various types of resins

www.freefoto.com

www.gizmodo.com.au

Ref.: N. Teng et al., *ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng.*, **7**, 8715-8723 (2019).
P. Froimowicz et al., *Chemsuschem*, **9**, 1921-1928 (2016).
N.K. Sini et al. *J. Polym. Sci., Part A : Polym. Chem.* **52**, 7-11 (2014).

Bio-based Benzoxazine

Vanillin

Stearylamine

Renewable resources

Eugenol

Furfurylamine

Bio-Based Epoxy Resin

Castor oil (CO) is obtained from the seeds of the CO plant.

- It is a low-cost vegetable oil, long shelf life, low toxicity, low-viscosity liquid and easy availability.
- Over 90% of its fatty acid is ricinoleic acid.
- More ricinoleic acid impart a higher reactivity than other vegetable oils such as soy, sunflower, canola and so on.
- It can be applied as plasticizer, lubricants and coating.

Epoxidized castor oil (ECO)

www.draxe.com/castor-oil

Properties of Carbon Nanotubes

- ❖ High capacity of converting the absorbed light to heat energy (e.g., optical absorption section)
- ❖ Strong absorbance over a wide wavelength range as compared to metal nanoparticles
- ❖ Absorb near infrared radiation (NIR) in small-sized carbon nanotubes
- ❖ Can be used to improve thermal stability of composites
- ❖ Exceptional mechanical properties such as extremely high modulus and stiffness

Ref : Q. Chen et al., *Polymer* . **47**, 7711-7719 (2006).
D. H. Yi et al., *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, **432**, 128-134 (2014).

Objectives

- To develop light-induced SMPs based on bio-based benzoxazine/epoxy copolymer reinforced with multiwalled carbon nanotubes.
- To investigate thermal, dynamic mechanical, and shape memory properties of bio-based benzoxazine/epoxy copolymer reinforced with multiwalled carbon nanotubes.

Preparation of Benzoxazine Resin

Experimental Procedure

Characterizations

Multiwalled carbon nanotubes

Benzoxazine Resin (V-fa)

Epoxidized castor oil

Specimen

T = 100°C
Stirred until
a homogeneous mixture

150°C/1h, 160°C/1h,
170°C/2h and 180°C/2h.

Results and Discussion

IR Spectra of V-fa/ECO Copolymer at 50/50 wt%

- The IR absorption spectrum of uncured V-fa/ECO mixture possessed IR absorption characteristics contributed from both V-fa and ECO.
- Epoxide groups can react with the phenolic hydroxyl group of the ring opened V-fa monomers to form new ether linkages and hydroxyl groups in epoxy moieties

DSC Thermograms of V-fa/ECO (50/50) Copolymer

Temperature range 25-300°C, Heating rate 10 °C/min

Curing Steps	Heat of Reaction (J g ⁻¹)	%Conversion
Uncured	160	-
150°C, 1hr	77	51.3
160°C, 1hr	30	81.3
170°C, 2hr	17	89.1
180°C, 2hr	8	94.8

$$\% \text{Conversion} = \left(1 - \frac{H_{\text{rxn}}}{H_0} \right) \times 100$$

H_{rxn} = heat of reaction of the partially cured specimen
 H_0 = heat of reaction of the uncured resin

Part I : V-fa/ECO Copolymers at Various V-fa Contents

Storage Modulus of V-fa/ECO Copolymer at Various V-fa Contents

V-fa/ECO Mass Content (wt%)	Storage Modulus (MPa) at -100°C
60/40	1.83×10^3
55/45	1.41×10^3
50/50	1.33×10^3
45/55	1.21×10^3
40/60	1.12×10^3
30/70	1.02×10^3

- The storage modulus was increased with an increase in V-fa contents.
- This result suggests that the addition of V-fa makes the copolymer more rigidity.

Loss Tangent of V-fa/ECO Copolymer at Various V-fa Contents

V-fa/ECO Mass Content (wt%)	Glass Transition Temperature, T_g (°C)	
	T_{g1}	T_{g2}
60/40	22	107
55/45	11	104
50/50	4	98
45/55	2	91
40/60	29	
30/70	2	

Temperature range of -100-200°C, Heating rate of 5 °C/min under N_2 atmosphere

Shape Fixity and Recovery of V-fa/ECO Copolymer at Various Contents

V-fa/ECO Mass Content	Shape Fixity, 25°C	Shape Recovery, $T_g+20^\circ\text{C}$	Glass Transition Temperature, T_g (°C)
45/55	79	97	91
50/50	86	97	98
55/45	87	95	104
60/40	90	92	107

➤ Increasing V-fa content enhanced shape fixity but decreased shape recovery.

Part II : V-fa/ECO (50/50) Composites at Various MWCNTs Contents

Storage Modulus of 50/50 V-fa/ECO Composites at Various MWCNTs Contents

MWCNTs (wt%)	Storage Modulus (MPa) at -100°C
0	1.33×10^3
0.1	1.44×10^3
0.3	2.01×10^3
0.5	1.03×10^3

➤ The storage modulus was increased with increasing MWCNTs at 0.1–0.3 wt%.

Loss Tangent of V-fa/ECO Composites at Various Various MWCNTs Contents

MWCNTs (wt%)	Glass transition temperature (°C)	
	T_{g1}	T_{g2}
0	4	96
0.1	6	102
0.3	17	106
0.5	4	98

- Addition of 0.3 wt% MWCNTs limited the molecular chain mobility and enhanced the glass transition temperature.

Transmission Electron Micrographs of V-fa/ECO Reinforced with MWCNTs

- MWCNTs were uniformly dispersed at 0.1 and 0.3 wt% MWCNT mass concentrations.
- Nanocomposite with the addition of 0.5 wt% MWCNTs showed aggregation of MWCNTs.

Shape Memory Properties

Shape Recovery under NIR-Actuation Processes

Shape Fixity of V-fa/ECO Composites at Various MWCNTs Contents Under NIR Laser

MWCNTs (wt%)	Shape Fixity at 25°C (%)
0	86
0.1	92
0.3	93
0.5	91

➤ MWCNTs can improve shape fixity of V-fa/ECO composite reinforced with MWCNTs at 0.1–0.3 wt%.

Shape Recovery of V-fa/ECO Composites at Various MWCNTs Contents under NIR Laser

MWCNTs (wt%)	Shape Recovery (%)
0	80
0.1	96
0.3	98
0.5	92

➤ Addition of 0.3 wt% MWCNT reinforced with V-fa/ECO composite providing the highest shape recovery during the shape recovery process.

Recovery Time under NIR-Actuation Vs Thermal Heating

MWCNTs (wt%)	Under NIR-Actuation (s)	Under Thermal Heating (s)
0	51	86
0.1	36	71
0.3	16	63
0.5	13	50

➤ Recovery time was decreased when increasing MWCNTs.

Repeated Fold-Deploy Cycles of V-fa/ECO SMPs

Shape fixity and shape recovery of V-fa/ECO reinforced with 0.3 wt% of MWCNTs versus deformation cycle

Conclusions

- MWCNT reinforced vanillin-furfurylamine-containing benzoxazine (V-fa)/epoxidized castor oil (ECO) composites with NIR-actuated shape memory effects were successfully fabricated.
- An addition of MWCNTs at mass concentrations of 0.1–0.3 wt% significantly improves dynamic mechanical properties and shape memory performances of the composites.
- The composites exhibited shape fixity of 92–93%, shape recovery of 96–98%, and shape recovery time of 36–16 s after an addition of MWCNTs at mass concentrations of 0.1–0.3 wt%.
- The temporary shape of the composite was efficiently recovered to the original shape under NIR actuation when compared to the shape recovery process under thermal triggering.
- Remote activation and site-specific shape recovery process under NIR irradiation could be realized for the composites.

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Thank You for Your Attention

